

MINDING THE GAP BETWEEN SECONDARY SCHOOL AND UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The renewal of engineering education requires an education that is more affected by students' circumstances which, if known, will help to guide them into the future. It is about channelling the students towards learning, taking into account the factors related to the acquisition of knowledge and how they can share this knowledge with the teachers. The specific aim of the current study was to examine what it means for students to transition from secondary school to university and introduce changes to reduce the failures it generates.

The causes of low grades in the initial phase of university are analysed; subsequently some remedies are included. First, to gather information, student surveys and interview activities, led by an expert, were conducted. Subsequently, compensatory actions were organized by experts, for students and teachers.

The surveys were designed to provide a self-assessment of new students regarding dedication and performance, and were given to those who failed the first important exam, capturing how they experienced university entrance and their first failure. They point to some personal causes of low performance: time organization deficiencies, impediments to devoting themselves to continuous study, and difficulties to adapt. Half believe their dedication merits better learnings and marks, and stress the difficulties associated with an insufficient level of secondary education and with the types of exams.

This study, encompassed within the framework of the activities dedicated to educational improvement at UPC, highlights the need to implement guidance and accompaniment actions devoted to first-year students.

1. INTRODUCTION

We address a widespread phenomenon among engineering students in the first year of university, although with differences depending on the competences, degrees and higher education systems concerned. Many students who begin engineering studies do not pass some subjects, others pass hardly any of them, and some leave, at the end of the academic year, or before. The abandonment of university studies wastes tens of millions of euros of public and/or private spending in universities and also frustrates the personal expectations of more than a third of Spanish university students. Spanish universities record high gross rates of global abandonment ranging from 37% to 50% [1]. Only a small percentage of students easily complete the initial phase during the academic year of their admission. The current project analyses this problem and tries to improve the situation. Failed subjects can negatively affect students in relation to their initial perception of university [2] and also their motivation to learn.

2 METHODOLOGY

Many teachers in many universities have thought about solutions to the problem. They have offered all students, free of charge, ways of achieving greater "inclusion": tutorial plans, seminars, adaptations of curricular workloads, recordings, multimedia

materials or environments with virtual reinforcements to facilitate comprehension, online self-assessment tests, flexible consultation schedules. But the problem remains.

At the Barcelona School of Agri-Food and Biosystems Engineering (EEABB) at UPC-Barcelona Tech, actions such as those described in the previous paragraph did not work for mathematics and chemistry, or did not work sufficiently. Due to the failure of so many initiatives of this nature, our group of teachers have now considered some forms more closely related to the accompaniment of students [3] and/or to specific features of the motivation of first-year students [4]. This is the "Mind the Gap" project. In particular, we have adopted a change in perspective and in the investigation of students suffering from the problem (or who at least appear to be candidates), what they think of themselves, the causes of the problem most attributable to themselves and, on the other hand, how they feel. In mathematics, the project is linked to one topic of the Special Interest Group in Mathematics (MSIG - SEFI): the activation of the students to ensure that they participate more in the learning process.

To this end, after the first major exams, and once the results were known, we addressed the students who had not passed them. In the 2019/20, 2020/21 and 2021/22 academic years, a survey was conducted with defined themes and closed and open questions. The response rate was sufficiently satisfactory, between 35% and 70% in different circumstances, for populations of between 80 and 100 students. The students were interviewed, looking for answers to questions concerning the issues described in the paragraph above: how they perceive their first academic failure, what level of demand they had in their way of working, and so on.

Students were asked the following questions, on qualitative more than quantitative aspects.

1. Do you think you have followed the subject?
2. What do you think about the knowledge you had when you got to university?
3. And about your learning capacity?
4. What dedication do you think you gave to the subject?
5. What was your weekly assignment of hours to the subject, in absolute terms?
6. And in relation to the other subjects?
7. What do you think about the relationship between dedication and results?
8. How do you value the virtual materials, based on their utility for study?
9. How do you value the interest of the different classes?
10. Have you used personal aid or external material resources such as private classes or classes in a training school outside the university?
11. Could you point to two topics that proved particularly difficult?
12. What was your mark in the exam?
13. What do you think your final mark will be?
14. With the experience you now have of the subject, what do you think you should improve?
15. Have you had personal situations making it difficult for you to follow the subject?

The desire to change the students' vision led teachers to ask for psychological and pedagogical information, about students' human traits, social forms and their attitudes, to help them discover the basics of the problem. The support was structured as a six-hour training activity conducted by an expert. Issues such as motivation, time management, adaptability, commitment, involvement and

awareness emerged, focusing on specific points. The assessment was positive. Reflection and debate on the role of the teacher arose, taking into account how current students arrive. The key role of the initial phase was emphasized, as it is the time when the student needs to form a link with the studies, and the importance of using tools to strengthen the student's commitment.

3 RESULTS AND IMPROVEMENT ACTIONS

In question 5, on weekly dedication to the subject, almost all the respondents answered two hours, one third of what ECTS credits require. In question 14, "With the experience you now have of the subject, what do you think you should improve?", the most common answers were: regularity in dedication (58%), organization of time (57%), motivation (45%), study technique (40%), prior knowledge (31%). According to surveys, the features that students see as low-performance causes are mostly personal: lack of organization of their time (non-continuous dedication) and problems in adapting to the university (their dedication does not correspond to enough learning or high enough marks). There are also more academic causes, notably the types of assessment and a deficient level of secondary education. This last response could encourage action to be taken in secondary education, but that has not been considered in this project as it is internal to the university.

First, actions were elaborated that would allow direct action on the roots of the problem, helping student persistence. This was done, above all, not in classical training fields (adhering to an academic aspect of training on the specific topics involved), but in more closely accompanying elements linked to positions, characteristics, customs and practices rooted in the students themselves.

The affected students took sessions in the field of psychological and pedagogical skills with the aim of altering their way of working and guiding them towards successful behaviours, with advice for a good first year at university, especially offering learning techniques to overcome organizational shortcomings. This was done with a free eight-hour workshop entitled "How to Improve My Academic and Personal Performance," which was well received by the attendees and found to be helpful. From this area, also follow-up, attention and help sessions were opened, with a view to welcoming new students, and extended throughout the first semester. Learning assistants (more experienced students) were also integrated, as these can help to overcome some limitations that are commonly experienced when integrating far-reaching actions into long courses [5].

By way of conclusion, the project has led to greater awareness of the problem among the entire group. It has been seen that there are important extra-academic factors for failure, that students need support actions to overcome this type of difficulty and that it is important that the university transmits this support.

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